

THE IMPORTANCE OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY IN TEACHING ENGLISH AS A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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ABSTRACT

In this study, students' language competence and the knowledge using information technology are mentioned as essential skills to have.

In the last decades, the world has changed its attitude towards all fields of life and elements of learning too. Education, especially higher education, is seen as the leading factor in social, political and economic progress. The reason for this attention is obvious by understanding that the most important value and the main capital of modern society is a person capable of finding and mastering new knowledge and adopting non-standard solutions. This capital, in its turn, is formed precisely in the system of higher education - in universities, institutes, higher schools, academies and other institutions. Uzbekistan is among the states where there is a clear understanding of the strategic importance of the educational sphere for the development of the country.

The Strategy of Actions on Further Development of Uzbekistan for the period 2017-2021 has given a new impetus to the

efforts of improving the system of training highly qualified specialists, teachers and researchers on the basis of modern requirements and the introduction of advanced foreign experience. The most important task of adopted resolution is equipping the higher educational institutions with modern information and communication technologies. It is vital to train highly qualified specialists in the higher education system capable of operating in high-tech industries.

At the same time, all attention now needs to focus more on ensuring the quality of teaching English.

In particular, it is necessary to provide:

- the modernization of curricula and programs, taking into account best international practices;

- strengthening of mechanisms to encourage knowledge of the English language;

- the widespread introduction in English teaching of modern information and communication technologies.

As an example of developed countries, there is a distance learning in various higher educational institutions, in order to increase the information technology and language competence on students.

Programme iSpring allows teachers to develop professional distance courses directly in PowerPoint quickly and without special preparation. Another good point of this programme is quiz. With the help of iSpring products, distance education is provided by auto dealers and airlines, banks and insurance organizations, oil and gas and metallurgical companies, IT companies and foreign universities. Both teachers and

students can create interactive tests and surveys to improve the learning process:

1. 23 types of questions, including drag-and-drop
2. Scenarios of branching between questions
3. Customizable test questions design
4. Add audio and video

Allows to record the voice acting to the test questions directly in the editor and add notifications to audio, images, formulas, and configure default messages for correct and incorrect answers. With iSpring Suite 8, you can quickly create tests and polls. The program offers advanced options for setting up test rules and scoring. Use 11 types of assessment questions and 12 types of

questionnaire questions. This will allow for a qualitative test of students' knowledge.

Summing up, we would like to say that information technologies have a huge impact on human life and their introduction into the educational system is caused by

everyday necessity. In our life, computers, high-speed access to the World Wide Web and technical multimedia capabilities are easy to enter. It would be inexcusable not to use with maximum efficiency what literally "lies underfoot".

References:

1. The Republic of Uzbekistan (2017). "The Strategy of Actions on Further Development of Uzbekistan ". Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan №UP-4947 on February 7, 2017
2. Republic of Uzbekistan (2015). "On measures to further improve the system of retraining and advanced training for managers and teaching staff of higher educational institutions." Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan.